

SARAS CALL h2020-ICT-2016-2017

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

SARAS

“Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon”

D5.1 – 3D modelling of anatomy and 3D registration

Due date of deliverable: June 28, 2019

Actual submission date: June 28, 2019

Grant agreement number: 779813
Start date of project: 01/01/2018

Lead contractor: Università di Verona
Duration: 36 months

Project funded by the European Commission within the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation HORIZON 2020	
Dissemination Level	
PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
Int = Internal Working Document	

D5.1 – 3D modelling of anatomy and 3D registration

Editors

Francesco Setti (UNIVR)
Riccardo Muradore (UNIVR)

Contributors

Nicola Piccinelli (UNIVR)
Andrea Roberti (UNIVR)
Giacomo De Rossi (UNIVR)
Fabio Falezza (UNIVR)

Reviewers

All partners

The work described in this document has been conducted within the project SARAS, started in January 2018. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.779813.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	6
2	Endoscope calibration	7
2.1	Camera model	8
2.2	Stereo camera calibration	9
2.3	Eye-to-Hand calibration and world registration	13
3	3D reconstruction	15
3.1	Stereo vision and point cloud triangulation	16
3.1.1	Baseline and depth range estimation	16
3.1.2	Point cloud generation and evaluation	17
3.2	Pre-operative phantom model	17
4	Monocular SLAM and map registration	20
4.1	Kinematics for scaled SLAM	20
4.2	Map registration	25
5	Map update	36
6	Discussion on current technologies	36
6.1	Endoscope with larger baseline	38
6.2	Endoscope with RGB and depth sensor	40

List of Figures

1	Optical layout of a rigid endoscope (credits to Lighthouse Imaging).	8
2	Chessboard calibration pattern.	9
3	Some example pairs of images used for calibration.	10
4	Example of results of corner detection and chessboard reconstruction on the camera plane.	10
5	Graphical explanation of reprojection error computation.	11
6	Reprojection error over the calibration image pairs.	11
7	Reconstructed calibration planes and camera positioning.	12
8	Estimated relative camera positioning.	12
9	Some example pairs of images with selected control points and the related epipolar line.	13
10	Some example pairs of images with selected control points with the reference board located at 100 mm and 50 mm from the cameras.	13
11	ArUco marker for Eye-to-hand calibration	15
12	A 3D reconstruction of the da Vinci large needle driver placed over the bladder phantom.	17
13	The 3D reconstruction of the da Vinci large needle driver compared with the forward kinematics of the TCP.	17
14	A phantom used for the validation. The SfM must be done every time a new phantom is used.	18
15	The different phases of the initial map reconstruction. a) the output of the SfM pipeline, b) the outcome of the outlier removal, c) the surface reconstruction for the hole filling, d) the final reconstruction merging the original point cloud with the sampled surface.	19
16	The registration of the preoperative map. The green dots are part of the point cloud obtained by SLAM, the initial map is shown in purple. The reference frame shows the endoscope position registered with respect to the common reference frame. . . .	25
17	The results of the ICP registration and a comparison with the real world. a) the registration results of the sparse map (green points) built by SLAM and the dense point cloud previously generated by SfM, b) a comparison between the real world configuration and the sensed one.	26
18	The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a, b) the captured left and right images	38
19	The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a, b) the catheter segmentation mask	39

20	The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a) the point cloud obtained through ELAS, b) the catheter grasping point triangulated from the colour-based segmentation	39
21	The results of the grasping point segmentation and triangulation. a) the point cloud obtained using the RGBD sensor b) the catheter grasping point obtained by the colour-based segmentation.	40

List of Tables

1	The reference tool extents are manually measured, the position is obtained by the forward kinematics and is expressed with respect to the reference frame of the camera. The measurement on the point cloud are also expressed in the same reference frame.	17
---	---	----

1 Introduction

This deliverable will report on the set of tools for 3D modelling of the human anatomy and 3D registration from intra-operative (i.e. endoscopic images) and pre-operative data (e.g. MRI scans).

The 3D reconstruction of the anatomy will be carried out by exploiting the most advanced 3D vision techniques, including stereo and multi-view geometry, Simultaneous Location and Mapping (SLAM) and non-rigid structure-from-motion.

In this document we will present all the work that has been performed during the SARAS project to allow the system to automatically generate a 3D map of the anatomical environment. With respect to standard 3D reconstruction applications, our scenario presents specific challenges that make the problem extreme. First of all the structures (i.e. organs) we are interested in reconstruct are highly deformable, with no reliable dynamical models available in advance. Furthermore, the anatomical structures are connected to each other by means of fat, vessels and connective tissues with high variability in mechanical properties, which makes the behaviour of these connections unpredictable. Lastly, the variability of shape, dimensions and appearance of these structures is extremely high, so to make impossible to use a *prototype model* to be used for the majority of the subjects as prior knowledge.

In the rest of this document we will provide details and discussions about all the main phases involved in this task, including system calibration, multiple view geometrical reconstruction and integration with the robot kinematics.

In Section 2 we present all the technical aspects related to the calibration of the vision system, both in terms of camera calibration and camera-robot calibration to make the results of 3D reconstruction of the anatomical environment available in an appropriate reference frame, i.e. registered with the robotic arms operating in that workspace.

The 3D reconstruction of the anatomy, including point cloud triangulation and structure from motion is presented in Section 3; monocular SLAM and 3D registration with respect to the *a priori* 3D map is detailed in Section 4.

With respect to the original description of this deliverable available in the Grant Agreement, we decided to drop the automatic map update section. After receiving constructive feedbacks from medical doctors: a dynamical registration of a pre-operative map would become useless after only a few minutes due to the ever-changing nature of the anatomical scenario. We comment on this point in Section 5.

Following the SARAS vision, in this work we only used available technologies (i.e. instruments) already certified and available as medical devices. Despite that, in Section 6 we discuss new technologies that can be useful in this task and their potential implementation into our project.

2 Endoscope calibration

The development of an effective method for geometric calibration of a medical endoscope is a well known yet still challenging task [15]. We cite three main reasons for which this problem is an endeavour by itself [1]:

1. in general, the calibration result has to be extremely accurate since it is directly involved in providing guidance for high accuracy medical procedures;
2. the endoscope optics introduces strong radial distortions that require special consideration in the projection model; it is due to the small aperture and relatively large field of view of the optics;
3. the calibration procedure has to be performed by a non-expert in the Operating Room (OR), which requires the method to be simple, fast and robust.

2.1 Camera model

Rigid endoscopes can contain up to 60 lens components for relaying the image through the inside of its tubular body. Diameters of optical components can be 1 mm or less. In the last decade the market asked for advanced endoscopes with superior brightness and resolution and smaller diameter, as a result lens quality in term of distortion was not a priority for manufacturers.

The rigid endoscope optical design is similar to that of a periscope, and is shown in Figure 1. The objective lens system forms an inverted image of the internal organ to be observed. A field lens placed near the image redirects the chief ray towards the centre of the relay lens system. Another field lens keeps the chief ray confined to the small diameter of the endoscope needle. This succession of relay lenses and field lenses is repeated as necessary for the required insertion depth of the instrument. A conventional ocular magnified the image.

Figure 1: Optical layout of a rigid endoscope (credits to Lighthouse Imaging).

Despite the complex structure of the optics and the resulting complex camera model, we decided to use the classic pin-hole camera model as a first approximation. We will prove experimentally that this approximation is compatible with the target accuracy we want to achieve and thus there is no need to use a more complex distortion models, like the one proposed in [1].

2.2 Stereo camera calibration

Geometric camera calibration under the pinhole camera model assumption is a well studied topic, and currently several methods and software are available for accomplishing the task. We decided to rely on the Zhang's method [17], and specifically we used the Bouget's implementation of this method which is available in both the `OpenCV` library and in Matlab. For the sake of clarity in presentation, we will report results and images from the Matlab procedure in the rest of this section.

This procedure requires the acquisition of a minimum of three pairs of images of a calibrated chessboard. Best results can be achieved by using between 10 and 20 images of the calibration pattern. Some attention has to be posed to the proper design and usage of the calibration pattern and the camera setup to work with the calibrator.

The calibration accuracy is strongly dependent on the dimension of the calibration pattern, i.e. the density of feature points detected in the calibration images. In this project we use the standard chessboard pattern proposed in the literature and shown in Figure 2. With respect to other patterns proposed in the literature (e.g. dotted grid) the chessboard provides more accurate points localisation and it is more robust to light changes.

www.calib.io | 6x8 | Checker Size: 15 mm.

Figure 2: Chessboard calibration pattern.

The optimal ratio between chess size and operative distance –i.e. the distance between camera and chessboard– has been investigated experimentally in our setup. We tested several configurations in a range between 20mm and 80mm and for each of them we ran the calibration routine and test the quality using the re-projection and the epipolar error (which measures the distance of one point to the epipolar line drawn from the same point localised on the other camera). Our results confirm findings in the literature that report an optimal distance ratio vs chess size of about 10 to 20 [8].

According to this study and our experiments we decided to use a calibration chessboard with chess size of 15mm at a distance ranging from 150mm to 300mm. Some example images are shown in Figure 3. We acquired 16 pairs of images. During the procedure, we had to reject 6 pairs due to poor quality (mainly because of the chessboard was not visible in its entirety), resulting in 10 pairs of valid images.

Figure 3: Some example pairs of images used for calibration.

The first step in camera calibration is to extract all the corners in the image and reconstruct the chessboard grid on the image plan. We used the Harris–Stephens algorithm [5] to find these feature points and some example results are reported in Figure 4. In this figure we can see corners marked with a green circle, the origin of the reference frame marked with a yellow square, and the direction of the x-axis on the top of the left image.

Figure 4: Example of results of corner detection and chessboard reconstruction on the camera plane.

After finishing with the optimisation procedure, we can evaluate calibration accuracy by examining the reprojection errors and the camera extrinsic parameters.

The *reprojection errors* are the distances measured in pixels between the detected and the reprojected points in the image plane. We calculate reprojection errors by projecting the checkerboard points

from world coordinates into image coordinates and comparing them to the corresponding detected points. A graphical explanation of how this is computed is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Graphical explanation of reprojection error computation.

As a general rule, reprojection errors of less than one pixel are acceptable. In our case, we can achieve much better results with an average reprojection error over all the calibration images of 0.412 pixels. Moreover, all the images present a subpixel reprojection accuracy with a maximum value of 0.647 pixels (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Reprojection error over the calibration image pairs.

Calibration results can also be qualitatively interpreted by visualising the *extrinsic parameters* of the stereo camera. In Figure 7 we can see the reconstructed position of all the planes –i.e. the chessboards– used in calibration as well as the localisation of the stereo pair in the origin of the

reference frame. This picture confirms the good results of calibration because all the planes are located at a distance from the cameras between 150 and 300 mm, as expected.

Figure 7: Reconstructed calibration planes and camera positioning.

A closer look at the relative camera positioning is in Figure 8. Again, we can confirm that calibration is successful since the two cameras are parallel and the baseline between the two optical centres is 5.508 mm, compatible with the nominal parameters of the endoscope.

Figure 8: Estimated relative camera positioning.

We provide a further evaluation of the camera calibration procedure by means of visually checking the epipolar planes. We evaluate the quality of epipolar plane estimation by visualising the epipolar lines generated by some points on a reference board. Figure 9 reports some sample points (yellow marker on the right side image) and the related epipolar line (in red on the left side image).

Figure 9: Some example pairs of images with selected control points and the related epipolar line.

The last validation we provide on the stereo calibration procedure is to demonstrate the generalisation capability of these camera parameters to be able to work in the whole workspace of the endoscopic device. While in general the operative range of an instrument should be limited to the operative conditions spanned during calibration, in this case we want to demonstrate that our calibration is able to provide good results even when the target objects are closer to the camera plane. To do that, we tested two different target objects (again the same reference board of the previous test) at a distance of about 100 mm and 50 mm. In both cases we have a very precise epipolar line generation and thus we can assume 3D reconstructions will be as good as in the operative range (with the only constraint that the image processing technique devoted to feature point matching could need some adaptation). Results are reported in Figure 10. This concludes our stereo camera calibration procedure and we can move to the next steps of the system calibration.

Figure 10: Some example pairs of images with selected control points with the reference board located at 100 mm and 50 mm from the cameras.

2.3 Eye-to-Hand calibration and world registration

Thanks to the use of ROS, every relative transform between poses is inserted into a tree by "father-child" frame dependency that can be interrogated at any time to obtain every possible transformation in the virtual space; for example it allows to query the position of the left SARAS tool with respect to the left camera. Since all tool manipulators and the endoscope camera arm already provide reliable kinematic positions that can be used to map their pose in space (after the global frame registration

is correctly executed), the only pose transformation missing is the one between the left/right stereo camera assembly and the the camera arm in which it is embedded. Such mapping is known as *Eye-to-Hand calibration* [14]. Additionally, our interest lies in finding a simultaneous estimation of the pose of the camera with respect to the endoscope arm and the pose of the endoscope in the world, also known as solving an $\mathbf{AX} = \mathbf{ZB}$ problem for \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Z} as the eye-hand and world-base transformations to be determined.

Solving this problem is needed due to the limitations in the dVRK platform for which the relative positions of the manipulators and the endoscope are unknown. Following the notation in [13] and setting

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X} &= {}_c\mathbf{T}^t \\ \mathbf{Z} &= {}_0\mathbf{T}^b \\ \mathbf{A} &: \text{pose of the camera frame relative to the world } {}_0\mathbf{T}^c \\ \mathbf{B} &: \text{pose of the camera frame relative to the world } {}_b\mathbf{T}^t \end{aligned}$$

the solutions are the result of a iterative minimisation problem

$$\{ {}_c\mathbf{T}^t, {}_0\mathbf{T}^b \}^* = \arg \min_{{}_c\mathbf{T}^t, {}_0\mathbf{T}^b} \left(f({}_c\mathbf{T}^t, {}_0\mathbf{T}^b) + \lambda_3 \left\| {}_t\mathbf{R}^c {}_c\mathbf{R}^t - \mathbf{I} \right\|_F^2 + \lambda_4 \left\| {}_0\mathbf{R}^b {}_b\mathbf{R}^0 - \mathbf{I} \right\|_F^2 \right)$$

over the distance function f defined as

$$f({}_c\mathbf{T}^t, {}_0\mathbf{T}^b) = \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| {}_0\mathbf{R}^{c_i} {}_c\mathbf{R}^{t_i} - {}_t\mathbf{R}^{b_i} {}_b\mathbf{R}^{t_i} \right\|_F^2 + \lambda_2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| {}_0\mathbf{R}^{c_i} \mathbf{t}^{t_i} + {}_0\mathbf{t}_i^c - {}_0\mathbf{R}^{b_i} \mathbf{t}^{t_i} - {}_0\mathbf{t}^{b_i} \right\|_F^2$$

where λ_k are Lagrangian multipliers and $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Froebius norm operator. The matrix ${}_x\mathbf{R}^y$ and the vector ${}_x\mathbf{t}^y$ are the rotation and the translation of the corresponding homogeneous transformation matrix ${}_x\mathbf{T}^y$, respectively.

The pose transformation between the world and the camera, ${}_0\mathbf{T}^c$, is acquired through computer vision algorithms. Following the camera calibration procedure in Section 2, the camera needs to identify a known planar geometric structure positioned in the environment and place a Cartesian reference frame on it. This is achieved by using known markers, in our case *ArUco* markers, and solving a *Perspective-n-Point* (PnP) problem for which the solution is optimal whenever both the segmentation error of the marker and the reprojection error of the derived points are at a minimum.

The calibration procedure acquires multiple poses of the end effector on which the camera is attached to and the associated frames of the markers as recorded. To reduce both the initial positioning error and the marker estimate by the camera, the marker size has been set to 15 mm and the camera arm has been positioned to a distance of about 200mm. Nevertheless, the results for this calibration are, unfortunately, not precise enough w.r.t. the overall calibration error (i.e. with an order of magnitude difference), which introduces a high uncertainty in the location of the endoscope relative to the world and the other arms. This has repercussions especially in the placement of the 3D-reconstructed phantom in the world whenever the endoscope is re-positioned by the main surgeon towards the required operational area. Such error could be due to the dual optimisation problem currently implemented: given the mechanical constraint of the remote centre of motion of the endoscope arm, the cameras positioned at end effector of the latter are forced on a spherical surface; this removes the possibility of pure translations of the camera relative to the target, thus

the minimisation operates reliably only on the rotation. Additionally, each error in the estimate of ${}^c\mathbf{T}^t$ is reflected on ${}^0\mathbf{T}^b$, thus the final pose in space of the endoscope diverges from the reference.

Due to the limitations encountered in this calibration procedure, we are working on implementing a different one that will constraint the problem to become of type $\mathbf{AX} = \mathbf{XB}$, in which the transformation between the endoscope and the world ($\mathbf{Z} = {}^0\mathbf{T}^b$) is known a priori and the eye-to-hand is performed only once without the limitations of a remote centre of motion. An optimal solution to the aforementioned problem is presented in [6]. This represents a one-off calibration to establish with certainty the pose of the cameras.

Figure 11: ArUco marker for Eye-to-hand calibration

3 3D reconstruction

3.1 Stereo vision and point cloud triangulation

The stereo vision system is intended to provide a fully three-dimensional anatomical model of the environment to allow the SARAS system to accomplish tasks such as object segmentation, action recognition, decision making, and anatomical collision avoidance. We exploited the well known topic of binocular 3D reconstruction accounting high quality point cloud with stable scale and shape. Geometry of the available instruments, i.e. the endoscope, pose several challenges and limit the precision achievable even with the most advanced computer vision methods. The main challenges are related to the very small baseline between the two cameras compared with the distance of the objects to be reconstructed. We will discuss this in Section 3.1.1. When moving to multiple view geometry and structure-from-motion techniques, other problems arise: on the one side, the camera motion is constrained by the remote centre of motion of the robotic arm again limiting the baseline available between different views; on the other side, the inherent deformable nature of anatomical structures does not allow for reliable triangulation of matched points within images acquired asynchronously. Nevertheless, with respect to standard SLAM and SfM algorithms, in our scenario we can leverage on the known camera position at each time step provided by the robot kinematics. Indeed this allow us to initialise the position of the 3D reconstructed point cloud and make the cloud registration easier, faster and more reliable than in the general case.

3.1.1 Baseline and depth range estimation

The vision system used in SARAS is the standard 12 mm stereo endoscope for the dVRK platform with a baseline distance between the cameras of approximately 5 mm. A major challenge involving the use of such a system is that it allows for a reliable 3D reconstruction only within a limited depth, i.e. when the point-of-view is sufficiently close to the target surface. The geometrical reason for this is discussed in [9]: the general depth estimation error ϵ_z grows quadratically with the distance, which means that the accuracy in the near range far exceeds that of the far range:

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{z^2}{bf} \epsilon_d,$$

where z is the depth, b is the stereo camera baseline, f is the focal length, and ϵ_d is the overall disparity error. Indeed, the higher the ratio between the baseline and the mean depth of the scene, the smaller the angle for the triangulation. In addition, when dealing with small objects far away from the camera the localisation of the point is less precise, i.e. the error on the epipolar line direction is higher. The combination of these two effects leads to low quality 3D reconstruction results. Luckily, evidences from the report on our MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform suggest that surgeons prefer to work with cameras on a distance of about 50 mm to 150 mm from the target structures, which is a good range for our purposes when associated to the more advanced feature extraction and point matching algorithms available in the literature.

3.1.2 Point cloud generation and evaluation

For the generation of the point cloud we use the *Efficient Large-Scale Stereo Matching* algorithm (ELAS) presented in [4]. As shown in Figure 12, we can provide a high quality point cloud reconstruction of the two da Vinci tools with very few missing points and a good-looking surface texture.

Figure 12: A 3D reconstruction of the da Vinci large needle driver placed over the bladder phantom.

To have a quantitative estimation of the reconstruction quality we measure length and width of the surgical tools and the relative position of the tool tips. We then compare results provided by 3D reconstruction with CAD models (for tool shape) and kinematic data (for relative position) provided by the multi-robot base calibration. A visualisation with superimposed reference frames and numerical results are reported in Figure 13 and Table 1.

Figure 13: The 3D reconstruction of the da Vinci large needle driver compared with the forward kinematics of the TCP.

	Length (m)	Width (m)	Position (m)
Reference	0.0060	0.0040	(0.0095, 0.0054, 0.0363)
Point cloud	0.0061	0.0046	(0.0044, 0.0029, 0.0344)

Table 1: The reference tool extents are manually measured, the position is obtained by the forward kinematics and is expressed with respect to the reference frame of the camera. The measurement on the point cloud are also expressed in the same reference frame.

3.2 Pre-operative phantom model

The preoperative model of a patient is generally obtained using some imaging techniques like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) or Computerised Axial Tomography (CAT). In SARAS we do not

have access to these data since the material of the phantoms is not responsive to these technologies. We mimic the pre-operative data by modelling the phantom with an offline 3D reconstruction using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) algorithm. This technique uses a large set of images (generally hundreds or thousands of pictures) that can be taken with a mixture of devices, with different resolutions and not necessary calibrated. On this set, a multi-view approach is applied in order to reconstruct the scene geometry up to a scale factor. We generated this model with an Intel RealSense D400 RGB-D camera that was manually moved in the space with no motion constraints.

Figure 14: A phantom used for the validation. The SfM must be done every time a new phantom is used.

The raw reconstruction provided by SfM is rather noisy and has some missing points (holes) due to reflection and failures in the local reconstruction of the surface. We use a post processing phase to mitigate these two effects as well as to find the optimal scaling factor which is not taken into account by SfM. We start with the scaling factor which is automatically computed by using an ArUco marker (see Figure 14) of known dimensions. We remove the outliers by using the denoising algorithm for point clouds proposed in [12]. Then we apply the following filtering steps:

- Remove the duplicated points by collapsing together the points which are closer than a user specified threshold;
- Reconstruct a smooth interpolated surface using Poisson method in order to 'close' possible holes on the surface. Figure 15c shows an example of the reconstructed surface;
- Sample points on the surface using the method presented in [3] in order to obtain the final point cloud.

Figure 15d shows the final point cloud.

(a) SfM output

(b) Outlier removal

(c) Surface reconstruction

(d) Final reconstruction

Figure 15: The different phases of the initial map reconstruction. a) the output of the SfM pipeline, b) the outcome of the outlier removal, c) the surface reconstruction for the hole filling, d) the final reconstruction merging the original point cloud with the sampled surface.

4 Monocular SLAM and map registration

In Section 3 we discussed the limitations on the working distance for a reliable and appropriate 3D reconstruction of the scene; this leads to a limitation on the field of view which is proportional to the focal length of the cameras. In addition, the cameras cannot be arbitrarily moved since they are controlled by the main surgeon and are constrained to rotate and translate with respect to a fixed remote centre of motion. To overcome these limitations we introduced a preliminary step to build a nominal model of the anatomical scene at the initial stage of the surgical procedure and register it with the pre-operative model discussed in Section 3.2.

Right after the insertion of the endoscope into the trocar, before starting the surgical procedure, we ask the surgeon to move the camera spanning as much of the workspace as possible in order to visually cover all the anatomical structures in the scene. We process these images with a monocular SLAM method which progressively builds a sparse point cloud of the scene. As shown in [2] this is an appropriate way to provide a 3D environment regardless the position of the vision system w.r.t the surrounding environment. In [2] the registration is used only to provide augmented reality to surgeon; in our case we adopt the same approach to project in real time the preoperative information into the scene. The SLAM algorithm used for the registration is based on ORB-SLAM [7].

This nominal model obtained is then registered to the pre-operative model to define a common reference frame between the two. Although the anatomy rapidly changes during the surgery, this registration is useful for many reasons, e.g. avoiding collisions with rigid anatomical structures like the pelvic bones and predicting interaction forces with the deformed organs. The registration is a two-step procedure.

In the *first step* we find an initial transformation between the two point clouds based on the minimisation of the mean square distance between two sets of corresponding fiducial points. These points are detected using the shape descriptor presented in [16] called *Intrinsic Shape Signatures* (ISS). The detected key-points are then encoded using a local feature descriptors called *Fast Point Feature Histograms* (FPFH) [10], [11]. This transform is used as the initial guess for the *Iterative Closest Point* (ICP) technique that minimise the distance between two sets of points with no association required (*second step*). Even though the ICP procedure does not guarantee that matched points remain associated throughout the processing and in the final results, it has been extensively demonstrated that the procedure converges with higher reliability if the initial guess is sufficiently close to the correct solution. For this reason we are confident that our procedure will give reliable results and our tests confirm this hypothesis.

From the implementation point of view, the registration routines exploit the open source point cloud library `pcl`. The monocular SLAM and 3D registration implementations are available in the ROS package `monocular_slam_registration`.

4.1 Kinematics for scaled SLAM

SLAM algorithms, similarly to SfM, can only provide 3D models up to an unknown scaling factor. In the previous section we estimated such factor by manually measuring a marker visible in both the reconstructed phantom and the real phantom. In the SLAM solution, we solve the scaling ambiguity at the initialisation of the mapping procedure in order to have the correct scaling even if

the environment reconstruction is not finished.

ORB-SLAM estimates the scaling factor using the inverse of the mean depth of the scene, in this way it is able to compute a constant scale which does not depend on the camera trajectory followed during the initialisation phase. To ease the convergence of the ICP procedure, we need to have a perfect matching between the initial map size and the SLAM environment scale. For this reason we slightly modified ORB-SLAM in order to use the kinematics for the computation of the scene scale.

We start recording the pose of the camera during the SLAM initialisation procedure. As soon as the first map reconstruction is available, we update the estimated camera position with the relative transformation between the first and the last kinematics poses. Then, we scale the computed map points by the ratio between the estimated camera trajectory and the relative kinematics trajectory. The scale estimation process assumes the trajectory of camera during the SLAM initialisation to be a pure translation movement. Unfortunately, in our case, since the endoscope is mounted on an arm with a remote centre of motion, the only possible movement is along the endoscope axis.

To delve into the implementation details, we provide the relevant code extract implementing such procedure.

```
1  ...
2  void Tracking::MonocularInitialization()
3  {
4      if (!mpInitializer)
5      {
6          // Set Reference Frame
7          if (mCurrentFrame.mvKeys.size() > 100)
8          {
9              // Record the initial kinematics pose of the camera
10             cam_pose.copyTo(initial_cam_pose);
11
12             mInitialFrame = Frame(mCurrentFrame);
13             mLastFrame = Frame(mCurrentFrame);
14             mvbPrevMatched.resize(mCurrentFrame.mvKeysUn.size());
15             for (size_t i = 0; i < mCurrentFrame.mvKeysUn.size(); i++)
16                 mvbPrevMatched[i] = mCurrentFrame.mvKeysUn[i].pt;
17
18             if (mpInitializer)
19             {
20                 delete mpInitializer;
21             }
22
23             mpInitializer = new Initializer(mCurrentFrame, 1.0, 200);
24             fill(mvIniMatches.begin(), mvIniMatches.end(), -1);
25             return;
26         }
27     }
28     else
29     {
30         // Try to initialize
31         if ((int)mCurrentFrame.mvKeys.size() <= 100)
32         {
33             delete mpInitializer;
34             mpInitializer = static_cast<Initializer *>(NULL);
35             fill(mvIniMatches.begin(), mvIniMatches.end(), -1);
36             return;

```

```

37     }
38
39     // Find correspondences
40     ORBmatcher matcher(0.9, true);
41     int nmatches = matcher.SearchForInitialization(
42         mInitialFrame, mCurrentFrame,
43         mvbPrevMatched, mvIniMatches, 100);
44
45     // Check if there are enough correspondences
46     if (nmatches < 100)
47     {
48         delete mpInitializer;
49         mpInitializer = static_cast<Initializer *>(NULL);
50         return;
51     }
52
53     // Current Camera Rotation
54     cv::Mat Rcw;
55     // Current Camera Translation
56     cv::Mat tcw;
57     // Triangulated Correspondences (mvIniMatches)
58     vector<bool> vbTriangulated;
59
60     if (mpInitializer->Initialize(
61         mCurrentFrame, mvIniMatches,
62         Rcw, tcw, mvIniP3D, vbTriangulated))
63     {
64         for (size_t i = 0, iend = mvIniMatches.size(); i < iend; i++)
65         {
66             if (mvIniMatches[i] >= 0 && !vbTriangulated[i])
67             {
68                 mvIniMatches[i] = -1;
69                 nmatches--;
70             }
71         }
72
73         // Record the current kinematics pose of the camera
74         cam_pose.copyTo(current_cam_pose);
75
76         // Set Frame Poses
77         mInitialFrame.SetPose(cv::Mat::eye(4, 4, CV_32F));
78         cv::Mat Tcw = cv::Mat::eye(4, 4, CV_32F);
79         Rcw.copyTo(Tcw.rowRange(0, 3).colRange(0, 3));
80         tcw.copyTo(Tcw.rowRange(0, 3).col(3));
81         mCurrentFrame.SetPose(Tcw);
82
83         CreateInitialMapMonocular();
84     }
85 }
86
87
88 void Tracking::CreateInitialMapMonocular()
89 {
90     // Create KeyFrames
91     KeyFrame *pKFinl = new KeyFrame(mInitialFrame, mpMap, mpKeyFrameDB);
92     KeyFrame *pKFcur = new KeyFrame(mCurrentFrame, mpMap, mpKeyFrameDB);

```

```

93
94     pKFini->ComputeBoW();
95     pKFcur->ComputeBoW();
96
97     // Insert KFs in the map
98     mpMap->AddKeyFrame(pKFini);
99     mpMap->AddKeyFrame(pKFcur);
100
101     // Create MapPoints and associate to keyframes
102     for (size_t i = 0; i < mvIniMatches.size(); i++)
103     {
104         if (mvIniMatches[i] < 0)
105             continue;
106
107         //Create MapPoint.
108         cv::Mat worldPos(mvIniP3D[i]);
109
110         MapPoint *pMP = new MapPoint(worldPos, pKFcur, mpMap);
111
112         pKFini->AddMapPoint(pMP, i);
113         pKFcur->AddMapPoint(pMP, mvIniMatches[i]);
114
115         pMP->AddObservation(pKFini, i);
116         pMP->AddObservation(pKFcur, mvIniMatches[i]);
117
118         pMP->ComputeDistinctiveDescriptors();
119         pMP->UpdateNormalAndDepth();
120
121         //Fill Current Frame structure
122         mCurrentFrame.mvpMapPoints[mvIniMatches[i]] = pMP;
123         mCurrentFrame.mvbOutlier[mvIniMatches[i]] = false;
124
125         //Add to Map
126         mpMap->AddMapPoint(pMP);
127     }
128
129     // Update Connections
130     pKFini->UpdateConnections();
131     pKFcur->UpdateConnections();
132
133     // Bundle Adjustment
134     Optimizer::GlobalBundleAdjustemnt(mpMap, 20);
135
136     if (pKFcur->TrackedMapPoints(1) < 100)
137     {
138         cout << "Wrong initialization, resetting..." << endl;
139         Reset();
140         return;
141     }
142
143     // Compute the transformation and set it as the slam camera pose
144     cv::Mat Tc2w = ComputeRelativeTransform(
145         initial_cam_pose, current_cam_pose);
146     pKFcur->SetPose(Tc2w);
147
148     // Compute the transformation between the slam camera and the

```

```

149 // kinematic
150 auto rel_T = ComputeRelativeTransform(Tc2w, mCurrentFrame.mTcw);
151
152 // Scale points
153 vector<MapPoint *> vpAllMapPoints = pKFin->GetMapPointMatches();
154 for (size_t iMP = 0; iMP < vpAllMapPoints.size(); iMP++)
155 {
156     if (vpAllMapPoints[iMP])
157     {
158         MapPoint *pMP = vpAllMapPoints[iMP];
159         cv::Mat temp = pMP->GetWorldPos();
160
161         cv::Mat newT = cv::Mat(4, 1, CV_32F);
162         newT.at<float>(0, 0) = temp.at<float>(0, 0);
163         newT.at<float>(1, 0) = temp.at<float>(1, 0);
164         newT.at<float>(2, 0) = temp.at<float>(2, 0);
165         newT.at<float>(3, 0) = 1.0f;
166
167         cv::Mat worldPose = rel_T * newT;
168         worldPose = worldPose/worldPose.at<float>(3, 0);
169
170         cv::Mat wp = (cv::Mat_<float>(3, 1) <<
171             worldPose.at<float>(0, 0),
172             worldPose.at<float>(1, 0),
173             worldPose.at<float>(2, 0));
174
175         pMP->SetWorldPos(wp * (1.0f/scaleKine));
176     }
177 }
178
179 mpLocalMapper->InsertKeyFrame(pKFin);
180 mpLocalMapper->InsertKeyFrame(pKFcur);
181
182 mCurrentFrame.SetPose(pKFcur->GetPose());
183 mnLastKeyFrameId = mCurrentFrame.mnId;
184 mpLastKeyFrame = pKFcur;
185
186.mvpLocalKeyFrames.push_back(pKFcur);
187.mvpLocalKeyFrames.push_back(pKFin);
188.mvpLocalMapPoints = mpMap->GetAllMapPoints();
189.mpReferenceKF = pKFcur;
190.mCurrentFrame.mpReferenceKF = pKFcur;
191
192.mLastFrame = Frame(mCurrentFrame);
193.mpMap->SetReferenceMapPoints(mvpLocalMapPoints);
194.mpMapDrawer->SetCurrentCameraPose(pKFcur->GetPose());
195.mpMap->mvpKeyFrameOrigins.push_back(pKFin);
196
197.mState = OK;
198 }
199 ...

```

4.2 Map registration

The registration of the SLAM to the map uses a feature-based initial alignment followed by a non linear least squares minimisation of the point-to-plane distance between the two clouds.

The point-to-plane method provides a more robust convergence and differs from the standard ICP technique since it requires the estimation of the normal unit vector on a neighbourhood for each point. For the pre-operative point cloud, as shown in Section 4, the normal vectors are pre-computed. For the sparse point cloud the normal vectors are computed just before the registration routine; the estimation process is also taking into account the camera position in order to have all the normal vectors pointing towards it. Finally to prevent convergence issues related to the different spatial sampling we voxelise the SLAM point cloud and the map to keep the same spatial point density.

Figure 16 shows a qualitative comparison of the registration of the SLAM with the initial map. the overall registration error (sum of squared distances from the SLAM point cloud to the corresponding target points) is of 0.0012 m.

Figure 16: The registration of the preoperative map. The green dots are part of the point cloud obtained by SLAM, the initial map is shown in purple. The reference frame shows the endoscope position registered with respect to the common reference frame.

In Figure 17 the same scene shown in Figure 16 is compared side by side with the real position of the endoscope with respect to the bladder.

```

1 #include <ros/ros.h>
2 #include <tf/transform_broadcaster.h>
3 #include <tf/transform_listener.h>
4 #include <sensor_msgs/PointCloud2.h>
5 #include <std_srvs/Empty.h>
6
7 #include <pcl_conversions/pcl_conversions.h>
8 #include <Eigen/Dense>
9
10 #include <pcl/point_cloud.h>
11 #include <pcl/point_types.h>
12 #include <pcl/features/fpfh.h>
13 #include <pcl/features/normal_3d_omp.h>
14 #include <pcl/registration/ia_ransac.h>
15 #include <pcl/filters/random_sample.h>
16 #include <pcl/filters/voxel_grid.h>
17 #include <pcl/common/transforms.h>
18 #include <pcl/io/ply_io.h>
19 #include <pcl/kdtree/kdtree_flann.h>
20 #include <pcl/common/transforms.h>

```


(a) SLAM registration

(b) Real world environment

Figure 17: The results of the ICP registration and a comparison with the real world. a) the registration results of the sparse map (green points) built by SLAM and the dense point cloud previously generated by SfM, b) a comparison between the real world configuration and the sensed one.

```

21 #include <pcl/keypoints/iss_3d.h>
22 #include <pcl/registration/correspondence_estimation.h>
23 #include <pcl/registration/correspondence_rejection_one_to_one.h>
24 #include <pcl/registration/correspondence_rejection_sample_consensus.h>
25 #include <pcl/registration/icp.h>
26 #include <pcl/registration/transformation_estimation_point_to_plane.h>
27 #include <pcl/registration/transformation_estimation_point_to_plane_lls.h>
28 #include <pcl/registration/transformation_estimation_svd.h>
29
30 #define SLAM_INITIAL_FRAME_NAME "/registrator/slam_ini"
31 #define SLAM_TRACKED_FRAME_NAME "/registrator/slam_tracked"
32 #define SLAM_MAP_REGISTERED "/registrator/map_registered"
33
34 tf::TransformBroadcaster *broadcaster;
35 tf::TransformListener *listener;
36
37 bool registered = false, slamReady = false;
38 Eigen::Matrix4f featTransformation, icpTransformation;
39
40 pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointXYZ>::Ptr cloud_slam;
41 pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr cloud_scene, subsample_cloud_scene,
42 cloud_slam_normals;
43 pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>::Ptr cloud_normals;
44
45 float voxel_size;
46 std::string map_path, reference_frame;
47
48 double computeCloudResolution(
49     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloud)
50 {
51     double resolution = 0.0;
52     int numberOfPoints = 0;
53     int nres;
54
55     std::vector<int> indices(2);

```

```

56     std::vector<float> squaredDistances(2);
57
58     pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointNormal> tree;
59     tree.setInputCloud(inputCloud);
60
61     for (size_t i = 0; i < inputCloud->size(); ++i)
62     {
63         if (!pcl_isfinite((*inputCloud)[i].x))
64         {
65             continue;
66         }
67
68         // Considering the second neighbor
69         // since the first is the point itself.
70         nres = tree.nearestKSearch(i, 2, indices, squaredDistances);
71         if (nres == 2)
72         {
73             resolution += sqrt(squaredDistances[1]);
74             ++numberOfPoints;
75         }
76     }
77
78     if (numberOfPoints != 0)
79     {
80         resolution /= numberOfPoints;
81     }
82
83     return resolution;
84 }
85
86 void keypointDetection(
87     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloud,
88     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr outputCloud)
89 {
90     pcl::ISSKeypoint3D<pcl::PointNormal, pcl::PointNormal> keys_det;
91     pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr tree(
92         new pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointNormal>());
93
94     double cloud_resol = computeCloudResolution(inputCloud);
95
96     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>::Ptr cldNormal(
97         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>);
98     pcl::copyPointCloud(*inputCloud, *cldNormal);
99
100    keys_det.setInputCloud(inputCloud);
101    keys_det.setNormals(cldNormal);
102
103    keys_det.setSearchMethod(tree);
104    keys_det.setMinNeighbors(3);
105    keys_det.setSalientRadius(6 * cloud_resol);
106    keys_det.setNonMaxRadius(4 * cloud_resol);
107    keys_det.setThreshold21(0.975);
108    keys_det.setThreshold32(0.975);
109    keys_det.setNumberOfThreads(4);
110
111    keys_det.compute(*outputCloud);

```

```

112 }
113
114 void featureExtraction(
115     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloud,
116     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputKeypoints,
117     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>::Ptr outputFeatures)
118 {
119     pcl::FPFHEstimation<
120         pcl::PointNormal, pcl::Normal,
121         pcl::FPFHSignature33> fpfh_est;
122     pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr tree(
123         new pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointNormal>());
124
125     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>::Ptr inputCloudNormal(
126         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>);
127     pcl::copyPointCloud(*inputCloud, *inputCloudNormal);
128
129     fpfh_est.setInputCloud(inputKeypoints);
130     fpfh_est.setInputNormals(inputCloudNormal);
131
132     fpfh_est.setSearchSurface(inputCloud);
133     fpfh_est.setSearchMethod(tree);
134     fpfh_est.setKSearch(8);
135
136     fpfh_est.compute(*outputFeatures);
137 }
138
139 void registration(
140     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputSourceCloud,
141     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>::Ptr &inputSourceFeatures,
142     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputTargetCloud,
143     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>::Ptr &inputTargetFeatures)
144 {
145     // estimate correspondences
146     pcl::registration::CorrespondenceEstimation<
147         pcl::FPFHSignature33, pcl::FPFHSignature33> est;
148     pcl::CorrespondencesPtr correspondences(new pcl::Correspondences());
149     est.setInputSource(inputSourceFeatures);
150     est.setInputTarget(inputTargetFeatures);
151     est.determineCorrespondences(*correspondences);
152
153     // Duplication rejection
154     pcl::CorrespondencesPtr correspondences_result_rej_one_to_one(
155         new pcl::Correspondences());
156     pcl::registration::CorrespondenceRejectorOneToOne corr_rej_one_to_one;
157     corr_rej_one_to_one.setInputCorrespondences(correspondences);
158     corr_rej_one_to_one.getCorrespondences(
159         *correspondences_result_rej_one_to_one);
160
161     // Correspondance rejection RANSAC
162     pcl::registration::CorrespondenceRejectorSampleConsensus<
163         pcl::PointNormal> rejector_sac;
164     pcl::CorrespondencesPtr correspondences_filtered(
165         new pcl::Correspondences());
166     rejector_sac.setInputSource(inputSourceCloud);
167     rejector_sac.setInputTarget(inputTargetCloud);

```

```

168     rejector_sac.setInlierThreshold(2.5);
169     rejector_sac.setMaximumIterations(1000000);
170     rejector_sac.setRefineModel(false);
171     rejector_sac.setInputCorrespondences(
172         correspondences_result_rej_one_to_one);
173
174     rejector_sac.getCorrespondences(*correspondences_filtered);
175     correspondences.swap(correspondences_filtered);
176
177     pcl::registration::TransformationEstimationSVD<
178         pcl::PointNormal, pcl::PointNormal>
179         transformation_estimation;
180     transformation_estimation.estimateRigidTransformation(
181         *inputSourceCloud, *inputTargetCloud,
182         *correspondences, featTransformation);
183 }
184
185 void featureBasedRegistration(
186     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloudSource,
187     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloudTarget)
188 {
189     // ISS keypoints
190     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr slam_keypoints(
191         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>);
192     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr scene_keypoints(
193         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>);
194     keypointDetection(inputCloudSource, slam_keypoints);
195     keypointDetection(inputCloudTarget, scene_keypoints);
196
197     // Extract features
198     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>::Ptr slam_features_(
199         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>);
200     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>::Ptr scene_features_(
201         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::FPFHSignature33>);
202     featureExtraction(inputCloudSource, slam_keypoints, slam_features_);
203     featureExtraction(inputCloudTarget, scene_keypoints, scene_features_);
204
205     // Registration
206     registration(
207         slam_keypoints, slam_features_,
208         scene_keypoints, scene_features_);
209 }
210
211 void rigidRegistration(
212     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloudSource,
213     const pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr &inputCloudTarget)
214 {
215     pcl::IterativeClosestPointWithNormals<
216         pcl::PointNormal, pcl::PointNormal> icp;
217     typedef pcl::registration::TransformationEstimationPointToPlane<
218         pcl::PointNormal, pcl::PointNormal> TE_t;
219     boost::shared_ptr<TE_t> teObj(new TE_t);
220     icp.setTransformationEstimation(teObj);
221
222     auto ransac_thr = voxel_size * 0.95;
223

```

```

224     icp.setMaximumIterations(100);
225     icp.setRANSACOutlierRejectionThreshold(ransac_thr);
226     icp.setMaxCorrespondenceDistance(ransac_thr * 10.0);
227     icp.setTransformationEpsilon(1e-12);
228     icp.setEuclideanFitnessEpsilon(1e-12);
229
230     // transform the point cloud with the feature based initial alignment
231     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr inputCloudSource_Reg(
232         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>());
233     pcl::transformPointCloud(
234         *inputCloudSource, *inputCloudSource_Reg,
235         featTransformation);
236
237     icp.setInputSource(inputCloudSource_Reg);
238     icp.setInputTarget(inputCloudTarget);
239
240     pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr cloud_slam_icp(
241         new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>());
242     icp.align(*cloud_slam_icp);
243
244     if (icp.hasConverged())
245     {
246         ROS_INFO("[SlamRegistration] ICP has converged with score: %f",
247             icp.getFitnessScore());
248         icpTransformation = icp.getFinalTransformation();
249     }
250     else
251     {
252         ROS_WARN("[SlamRegistration] ICP did not converge!");
253     }
254 }
255
256 void updateNormals(const tf::Vector3 &cP)
257 {
258     // Create the normal estimation class, and pass the input dataset to it
259     pcl::NormalEstimationOMP<pcl::PointXYZ, pcl::Normal> ne;
260     ne.setInputCloud(cloud_slam);
261
262     // Create an empty kdtree representation,
263     // and pass it to the normal estimation object.
264     // Its content will be filled inside the object,
265     // based on the given input dataset
266     // (as no other search surface is given).
267     pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointXYZ>::Ptr tree(
268         new pcl::search::KdTree<pcl::PointXYZ>());
269     ne.setSearchMethod(tree);
270
271     // Use all neighbors in a sphere
272     ne.setKSearch(16);
273
274     // Set the viewpoint
275     ne.setViewPoint(cP.x(), cP.y(), cP.z());
276
277     // Compute the features
278     ne.compute(*cloud_normals);
279 }

```

```

280
281 template <class T>
282 typename pcl::PointCloud<T>::Ptr voxelize(
283     typename pcl::PointCloud<T>::Ptr cld_in)
284 {
285     typename pcl::VoxelGrid<T> voxelizer;
286     voxelizer.setInputCloud(cld_in);
287
288     // leaf size in meters
289     voxelizer.setLeafSize(voxel_size, voxel_size, voxel_size);
290
291     typename pcl::PointCloud<T>::Ptr final_cld(
292         new typename pcl::PointCloud<T>);
293     voxelizer.filter(*final_cld);
294     return final_cld;
295 }
296
297 void init()
298 {
299     pcl::PLYReader Reader;
300     Reader.read(map_path, *cloud_scene);
301
302     subsample_cloud_scene = voxelize<pcl::PointNormal>(cloud_scene);
303
304     if (subsample_cloud_scene->size() > 0)
305     {
306         ROS_INFO("Model loaded");
307         ROS_INFO_STREAM("Subsampling (
308             voxel size: " << voxel_size << "): " <<
309             subsample_cloud_scene->size() << " points.");
310     }
311 }
312
313 void save()
314 {
315     // save last point cloud
316     pcl::PLYWriter writer;
317     writer.write<pcl::PointNormal>(
318         "/tmp/cloud_normals.ply",
319         *cloud_slam_normals, false, false);
320 }
321
322 void doReg()
323 {
324     // Do ICP and publish the registration
325     if (slamReady)
326     {
327         // Lookup the initial camera position
328         tf::StampedTransform cameraPose_transform;
329         try
330         {
331             listener->waitForTransform(
332                 reference_frame, SLAM_INITIAL_FRAME_NAME,
333                 ros::Time(0), ros::Duration(10.0));
334             listener->lookupTransform(
335                 reference_frame, SLAM_INITIAL_FRAME_NAME,

```

D5.1 – 3D modelling of anatomy and 3D registration

```
336     ros::Time(0), cameraPose_transform);
337
338     // align the sparse point cloud to the reference map
339     // and publish the transform in ROS compute normals
340     // for vertices
341     tf::Vector3 cP = cameraPose_transform.getOrigin();
342     updateNormals(cP);
343     pcl::concatenateFields(
344     *cloud_slam, *cloud_normals, *cloud_slam_normals);
345
346     featureBasedRegistration(
347     cloud_slam_normals, subsample_cloud_scene);
348     rigidRegitration(
349     cloud_slam_normals, subsample_cloud_scene);
350
351     registered = true;
352 }
353 catch (tf::TransformException ex)
354 {
355     ROS_ERROR("[Unable to register] %s", ex.what());
356     return;
357 }
358
359 }
360 }
361
362 void registrationLoop(const ros::Publisher& mp)
363 {
364     // Do ICP and publish the registration
365     if (slamReady)
366     {
367         // if at least one registration is done still publish
368         // the last transformation
369         if (registered)
370         {
371             //////////////////////////////////////
372             tf::Vector3 featOrigin;
373             tf::Matrix3x3 featTf3d;
374
375             featOrigin.setValue(
376                 featTransformation(0, 3),
377                 featTransformation(1, 3),
378                 featTransformation(2, 3));
379
380             featTf3d.setValue(
381                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(0, 0)),
382                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(0, 1)),
383                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(0, 2)),
384                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(1, 0)),
385                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(1, 1)),
386                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(1, 2)),
387                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(2, 0)),
388                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(2, 1)),
389                 static_cast<double>(featTransformation(2, 2)));
390
391             tf::Quaternion featTfqt;
```

D5.1 – 3D modelling of anatomy and 3D registration

```
392     featTf3d.setRotation(featsTfqt);
393
394     tf::Transform featTransform;
395     featTransform.setOrigin(featsOrigin);
396     featTransform.setRotation(featsTfqt);
397
398     //////////////////////////////////////
399     tf::Vector3 icpOrigin;
400     tf::Matrix3x3 icpTf3d;
401
402     icpOrigin.setValue(
403         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(0, 3)),
404         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(1, 3)),
405         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(2, 3)));
406
407     icpTf3d.setValue(
408         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(0, 0)),
409         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(0, 1)),
410         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(0, 2)),
411         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(1, 0)),
412         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(1, 1)),
413         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(1, 2)),
414         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(2, 0)),
415         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(2, 1)),
416         static_cast<double>(icpTransformation(2, 2)));
417
418     tf::Quaternion icpTfqt;
419     icpTf3d.setRotation(icpTfqt);
420
421     tf::Transform icpTransform;
422     icpTransform.setOrigin(icpOrigin);
423     icpTransform.setRotation(icpTfqt);
424
425     broadcaster->sendTransform(
426         tf::StampedTransform(
427             featTransform.inverse() * icpTransform.inverse(),
428             ros::Time::now(), SLAM_INITIAL_FRAME_NAME,
429             SLAM_MAP_REGISTERED));
430
431     // publish the reference point cloud w.r.t the new transform
432     sensor_msgs::PointCloud2 cloud2;
433     pcl::toROSMsg(*subsample_cloud_scene, cloud2);
434     cloud2.header.frame_id = SLAM_MAP_REGISTERED;
435     cloud2.header.stamp = ros::Time::now();
436     mp.publish(cloud2);
437 }
438 }
439 }
440
441 void SlamPointCloudUpdate(const sensor_msgs::PointCloud2ConstPtr &msg)
442 {
443     pcl::PCLPointCloud2 pcl_pc2;
444     pcl_conversions::toPCL(*msg, pcl_pc2);
445     pcl::fromPCLPointCloud2(pcl_pc2, *cloud_slam);
446
447     // point cloud voxelation to keep the same density of the map
```

```

448     cloud_slam = voxelize<pcl::PointXYZ>(cloud_slam);
449
450     // flag the output of the slam as available
451     slamReady = true;
452 }
453
454 bool RegisterInvoked(
455     std_srvs::Empty::Request &request,
456     std_srvs::Empty::Response &response)
457 {
458     try
459     {
460         registered = false;
461         doReg();
462
463         return true;
464     }
465     catch(const std::exception& e)
466     {
467         std::cerr << e.what() << '\n';
468         return false;
469     }
470 }
471
472 int main(int argc, char **argv)
473 {
474     ros::init(argc, argv, "Transform estimator");
475     ros::NodeHandle nh;
476     ros::NodeHandle pnh("~");
477     ros::Rate loop_rate(200);
478
479     broadcaster = new tf::TransformBroadcaster();
480     listener = new tf::TransformListener();
481
482     ros::Subscriber slamcloud_sub = pnh.subscribe(
483         "sparse_pointcloud", 1, &SlamPointCloudUpdate);
484     ros::Publisher scenecloud_pub = pnh.advertise<
485         sensor_msgs::PointCloud2>("map_pointcloud", 1);
486     ros::ServiceServer service = pnh.advertiseService(
487         "register", &RegisterInvoked);
488
489     pnh.param("voxel_size", voxel_size, 0.008f);
490     pnh.param("reference_frame", reference_frame, std::string(""));
491     pnh.param("map_path", map_path, std::string(""));
492
493     cloud_slam = pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointXYZ>::Ptr(
494     new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointXYZ>);
495     cloud_scene = pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr(
496     new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>);
497     subsample_cloud_scene = pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr(
498     new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>);
499     cloud_slam_normals = pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>::Ptr(
500     new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::PointNormal>);
501     cloud_normals = pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>::Ptr(
502     new pcl::PointCloud<pcl::Normal>);
503

```

```
504   init();
505
506   while (ros::ok())
507   {
508       registrationLoop(scenecloud_pub);
509
510       ros::spinOnce();
511       loop_rate.sleep();
512   }
513
514   save();
515
516   return 0;
517 }
```

5 Map update

In the original description of this deliverable it was planned to update the 3D map of the anatomical scene over the whole procedure. The goal was two-fold

1. estimate the interaction force of the tools with the anatomical structure by detecting the deformation using the images and multiplying such displacement by a stiffness matrix;
2. compute the anatomical forbidden regions for planning collision-free trajectories.

The update in real time of the 3D model turns out to be impossible due to the ever-changing nature of the anatomical scenario: the scene is not only deformed but substantially different (e.g. fat and organ removed). Then, we choose to use *strain gages* mounted along the shaft of the SARAS laparoscopic tools. Three strain gages at 120° around the shaft will provide voltages related to forces and torques at the tip of the tool. This is an on-going activity and we should be able to report on the manufacturing process and the calibration procedure at the end of the second year. The strain gages will be positioned between the tip and the trocar. We are aware that this solution cannot be used as it is in the operating room: however if this proof of concept will be successful, strain gages could be mounted inside the shaft of *ad hoc* tools to make the sterilisation process possible.

This solution allows us to have reliable force/torque measurements without the need to know the dynamical parameters of tissues and organs (e.g. stiffness). These parameters are very difficult to measure and they change according to the relative positioning of the organs.

Such direct measurements together with the robot kinematics and the video streaming could also be used to estimate the *bending* of the tools when interacting with the organs (e.g. pushing the bladder down, pulling the catheter, etc.). This is clearly an important aspect to be taken into account in the design of the low level controllers.

About the second point above, the position and volume of organs for computing collision-free trajectories can be estimated by using the registered point cloud as explained in the previous section. The point cloud can be updated (or re-computed) using the SLAM algorithm any time big changes occur in the anatomical scenario (e.g. dissection of the prostate).

6 Discussion on current technologies

As highlighted in previous sections the mechanical constraint due to the trocar reduces the workspace and the kind of motion of the da Vinci stereo endoscope. This limitation together with the small baseline between the two cameras within the endoscope badly affect the 3D reconstruction on which the autonomous system will rely on to correctly detect the phase of the procedure, to plan collision-free trajectories, and to promptly react to the surgeon commands in the next SOLO-SURGERY platform.

We observed experimentally that the vision system is not able to localise and/or reconstruct objects at a distant equal or larger than 15 cm to the tip of the endoscope. Basic tasks such as grasping threads or needle, or pushing/pulling small objects are very difficult.

For this reason we are going to present in this section two possible solutions to increase the workspace, improve the accuracy and relax the camera position constraints. We have defined two target tasks (taken from the prostatectomy procedure) to validate and compare the proposed approaches:

1. The identification and the 3D position estimation of the catheter;
2. The 3D reconstruction of anatomical surfaces.

The *identification and reconstruction tasks* are carried out in an operative configuration where the da Vinci endoscope vision system is not able to work efficiently (≈ 200 mm from the catheter), whereas the other visual solutions are in their operative range. The grasp of the catheter is a critical part of the prostatectomy: the assistant surgeon (or the SARAS system in our case) needs to detect the catheter using only the computer vision without any pre-operative information available. In fact the catheter is not part of the scene from the beginning of surgery but it 'appears' when the main surgeon is dissecting the prostate. The catheter is not tracked by any inertial or kinematic system and so it is a very interesting case to test the capability of different vision systems. The *3D reconstruction* is the second test case: we will compute dense and real-time surface reconstruction that allows to detect 3D objects on the scene. Despite SLAM, we do not need to move the camera for a long period of time.

The proposed solutions are the following:

1. A vision system with a larger baseline between the cameras in order to increase the operative range:
2. The integration of a depth sensor to be used together with the stereo system (e.g. the depth sensor could be placed on a separate endoscope).

The first solution would require the design of a brand new endoscope with a mechanical system able of increasing the baseline once inside the patient belly. In this report we use a commercial stereo camera as a proof of concept.

The second solution relies on a depth sensor which allows the 3D reconstruction using structured light. The light source is in the infrared spectrum, completely invisible to the surgeons, but able to provide very detailed 3D information of the environment even if the surface is really flat and without many features.

6.1 Endoscope with larger baseline

The following test aims to show how the baseline length affects the vision system accuracy. We used a commercial stereo camera to simulate an endoscope with a larger baseline (10 times larger) and to provides an insight of the detection and estimation capability of this kind of setup. The camera is a *Minoru3D* stereo camera with the following specifications:

Resolution 800×600

Frame rate 30 fps

Field of view 42°

Baseline 60 mm

Camera dimension Approx $110 \text{ mm} \times 70 \text{ mm} \times 30 \text{ mm}$

It is mounted on a fixed stand in front of the phantom.

The experiments show that we are able to track the catheter in real-time both using the image flow and the 3D reconstruction. The catheter, as shown in Figure 18a and 18b is segmented using a colour-based thresholding. For the purposes of the experiment, as shown in Figure 19a, 19b, we defined the grasping point as the lower point in the binary mask assuming the camera rotated accordingly.

Once the lower points are detected in the left and right images, it is possible to triangulate them and project the grasping point into the 3D space (world frame). Figure 20a shows the point cloud reconstructed using ELAS, whereas in Figure 20b the grasping point is superimposed on the environment scene.

Figure 18: The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a, b) the captured left and right images

(a) Left binary mask

(b) Right binary mask

Figure 19: The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a, b) the catheter segmentation mask

(a) Point cloud

(b) Grasping point estimation

Figure 20: The catheter segmentation process using the stereo camera. a) the point cloud obtained through ELAS, b) the catheter grasping point triangulated from the colour-based segmentation

6.2 Endoscope with RGB and depth sensor

In the second setup we used the commercial RGB-D sensor *RealSense D435* having the following technical specifications:

Depth technology Active IR stereo

Depth sensor FOV $87^\circ \pm 3^\circ \times 58^\circ \pm 1^\circ \times 95^\circ \pm 3^\circ$

Depth stream output resolution Up to 1280×720

Depth stream output frame rate Up to 90 fps

Minimum depth distance 0.1 m

RGB sensor resolution and frame rate 1920×1080 at 30 fps

RGB sensor FOV $69.4^\circ \times 42.5^\circ \times 77^\circ (\pm 3^\circ)$

Camera dimension $90 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm}$

It is mounted on a fixed stand in front of the phantom. Even if the experiments were conducted using an RGB and a depth sensor rigidly coupled to the chassis, this solution can be adapted to different scenarios. Knowing the relative transformation between the depth sensor and the colour sensor, it is possible to project the information about the texture of the surface onto the 3D reconstruction. It is worth highlighting that some problem may occur when the two sensors do not see the same scene due to occlusions.

As in the previous case, the catheter is segmented directly on the point cloud using a colour-based threshold. In Figure 21 are shown the results of the catheter segmentation and the environment point cloud generation.

(a) Point cloud

(b) Grasping point estimation

Figure 21: The results of the grasping point segmentation and triangulation. a) the point cloud obtained using the RGBD sensor b) the catheter grasping point obtained by the colour-based segmentation.

References

- [1] Joao Barreto, Jose Roquette, Peter Sturm, and Fernando Fonseca. Automatic camera calibration applied to medical endoscopy. In *British Machine Vision Conference (BMVC)*, 2009.
- [2] Long Chen, Wen Tang, Nigel W. John, Tao Ruan Wan, and Jian Jun Zhang. SLAM-based dense surface reconstruction in monocular Minimally Invasive Surgery and its application to Augmented Reality. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 158:135–146, 2018.
- [3] Massimiliano Corsini, Paolo Cignoni, and Roberto Scopigno. Efficient and flexible sampling with blue noise properties of triangular meshes. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 2012.
- [4] Andreas Geiger, Martin Roser, and Raquel Urtasun. Efficient large-scale stereo matching. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2011.
- [5] Christopher G. Harris and Mike Stephens. A combined corner and edge detector. In *Alvey Vision Conference*, 1988.
- [6] R. Horaud and F. Dornaika. Hand-eye calibration. *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, 14(3):195–210, 1995.
- [7] Raul Mur-Artal, J. M.M. Montiel, and Juan D. Tardos. ORB-SLAM: A Versatile and Accurate Monocular SLAM System. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 2015.
- [8] Veronica Penza, Andrea S. Ciullo, Sara Moccia, Leonardo S. Mattos, and Elena De Momi. EndoAbS dataset: Endoscopic abdominal stereo image dataset for benchmarking 3D stereo reconstruction algorithms. *International Journal of Medical Robotics and Computer Assisted Surgery*, 2018.
- [9] M. Pollefeys, J. Frahm, P. Mordohai, and D. Gallup. Variable baseline/resolution stereo. In *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2008.
- [10] Radu Bogdan Rusu, Nico Blodow, and Michael Beetz. Fast Point Feature Histograms (FPFH) for 3D registration. 2009.
- [11] Radu Bogdan Rusu, Andreas Holzbach, Nico Blodow, and Michael Beetz. Fast geometric point labeling using conditional random fields. In *2009 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, IROS 2009*, 2009.
- [12] Radu Bogdan Rusu, Zoltan Csaba Marton, Nico Blodow, Mihai Dolha, and Michael Beetz. Towards 3d point cloud based object maps for household environments. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 56(11):927–941, 2008.
- [13] K. H. Strobl and G. Hirzinger. Optimal hand-eye calibration. In *2006 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pages 4647–4653, Oct 2006.
- [14] R. Y. Tsai and R. K. Lenz. A new technique for fully autonomous and efficient 3d robotics hand/eye calibration. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, 5(3):345–358, June 1989.

- [15] Christian Wengert, Mireille Reeff, Philippe C Cattin, and Gábor Székely. Fully automatic endoscope calibration for intraoperative use. In *Bildverarbeitung für die Medizin*, pages 419–423. Springer, 2006.
- [16] Zhong Yu. Intrinsic shape signatures: A shape descriptor for 3D object recognition. In *2009 IEEE 12th International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops, ICCV Workshops 2009*, 2009.
- [17] Zhengyou Zhang. A flexible new technique for camera calibration. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 22(11):1330–1334, 2000.